

BLUEMISSION AA

Building a coordination hub to support the mission
implementation in the *Atlantic and Arctic Basin*

Report on Networking, collaboration and mutual learning for monitoring

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1. Introduction

1.1 BlueMissionAA and WP2

The EU Mission Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030 aims to restore the health of one of our most precious common goods: our ocean and waters. BlueMissionAA aims to build a coordination hub to support the Mission implementation in the Atlantic and Arctic Basin, focusing on preserving and restoring marine and coastal ecosystems and biodiversity for increase climate resilience. The Mission charter calls for joining efforts to achieve the following objectives:

- Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity, in line with the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030
- **Prevent and eliminate pollution** of our ocean, seas, and waters, in line with the EU Action Plan Towards Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil
- **Make the sustainable blue economy carbon-neutral and circular**, in line with the proposed European Climate Law and the holistic vision enshrined in the Sustainable Blue Economy Strategy.

Work Package 2 (WP2) focuses on monitoring and reporting, contributing to the evaluation of the implementation and progress of the Mission Ocean objectives, particularly in the restoration of marine ecosystems. To achieve this, several key activities have been undertaken:

- a baseline study of recent and ongoing EU and national R&I programmes, projects, and initiatives at basin level to identify relevant key performance indicators (KPIs);
- the development of a comprehensive monitoring framework and platform to automate data and information flows for effective monitoring and reporting;
- the adaptation of existing indicators as well as the identification and development of new indicators specific to the thematic focus of the lighthouse, to continuously track and report progress in the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse;
- the formulation of recommendations to support the mid-term evaluation and inform the Mission Ocean Work Programme 2025–2030; and
- close collaboration with the Mission Implementation Platform to align on monitoring needs.

Figure 1. Overview of Work Package 2

1.2 Aligning monitoring practices (Task 2.4)

The Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters” is one of the European Green Deal’s most ambitious initiatives, aiming to regenerate marine and freshwater ecosystems by 2030 through innovation, community engagement, and science-based action. Within this context, monitoring is not merely a technical requirement—it is a strategic instrument for guiding interventions, measuring progress, and ensuring transparency and accountability.

BlueMissionAA has played a pivotal role in reinforcing collaboration among Mission actors and aligning monitoring efforts across the ecosystem of Mission-funded projects and institutions. By promoting the proposed monitoring framework (Task 2.2) across other sea basin lighthouses, BlueMissionAA has helped enable ongoing tracking of progress, outcomes, and impacts in ecosystem restoration beyond the project’s duration. It has also fostered cross-basin knowledge exchange and contributed to strategic learning processes.

This report outlines key tools and mechanisms—such as WaveLinks (Task 3.1)—that have supported a more integrated and coherent approach to monitoring. It draws on lessons learned to inform future implementation efforts.

Monitoring within the Mission is both scientifically robust and socially embedded. It requires a strong understanding of ecological baselines, the ability to track restoration progress, and adaptability to the evolving conditions of Europe’s diverse water systems. Task 2.4 was designed to bridge the technical development of monitoring frameworks and tools—

including indicators and data infrastructure (Task 2.3)—with the broader Mission ecosystem, encompassing governance structures, stakeholders, and aligned initiatives.

This report presents the contributions of Task 2.4 in fostering shared learning, harmonising monitoring practices, and enabling feedback loops through interactions with the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP) (see 2.3.3), the European Commission (Mission Secretariat), PREP4BLUE, and the lighthouse CSAs: BlueMissionMed and BlueMissionBANOS. It also reflects on the role of WaveLinks as a collaborative platform for advancing monitoring and reporting practices.

Moreover, the integration of mutual learning tools - such as the PESTEL-informed Theory of Change framework - has added consistency and strategic depth to monitoring efforts across the Mission (see 3.1).

2. Networking and Liaison activities

2.1. The monitoring architecture of Mission Ocean and Waters

Throughout its implementation, BlueMissionAA has maintained active engagement with the broader coordination and monitoring architecture of the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters.” This has included regular participation in the Mission Coordinators’ Meetings (Monthly meeting with coordinators of CSAs and PREP4BLUE) - key venues for aligning strategic objectives, sharing progress updates, and coordinating efforts across all Mission-funded initiatives. In addition, the project has been a consistent contributor to the bi-monthly coordination calls led by PREP4BLUE’s partner ERRIN, supporting convergence on monitoring methodologies and fostering capacity-building across the Mission ecosystem (“Monitoring, Indicators, KPIs across Mission Ocean CSAs working group”).

These interactions have ensured that BlueMissionAA remains closely aligned with the overarching governance framework led by the European Commission and the Mission Secretariat. Discussions within these forums have addressed critical topics such as the harmonization of indicators, communication and outreach strategies, the rollout of the Mission Charter, and the integration of citizen science and stakeholder participation into monitoring approaches.

The project has benefited from a wide and diverse network of contributors to these exchanges, including leading scientific organizations like IFREMER, NIVA, and ICES; regional platforms such as the AIR Centre; and institutional partners like the European Environment Agency (EEA) and Technopolis Group, which supports implementation tracking through the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP). This collaborative ecosystem has enabled BlueMissionAA to stay embedded within the evolving Mission landscape and responsive to emerging priorities and challenges.

2.2. Interactions with the coordination and monitoring architecture

This section provides an overview of the key interactions established with the coordination and monitoring architecture of Mission Ocean and Waters. These interactions have taken place through various structured meetings and collaborative formats involving coordinators, CSAs, and key stakeholders. The purpose of these engagements is to ensure coherence across Mission activities, facilitate methodological alignment, and promote synergies between projects. Table 1 summarizes the main types of recurring meetings and events, along with their frequency, format, and typical agenda topics.

Meeting/Event Type	Frequency	Format	Typical Agenda Topics
Mission CSA Coordinators' Meetings	Monthly/Bi-monthly	Online	Policy updates, project synergies, joint actions, communications
Monitoring, Indicators, KPIs across Mission Ocean CSAs Working group (led by PREP4BLUE)	Bi-monthly	Online	Methodological alignment, capacity building, stakeholder mapping
cross-CSA-organized Workshops	As needed	Online or in-person	Thematic alignment, policy dialogues, showcasing best practices
Stakeholder Bilateral Meetings	As needed	Online or in-person	Technical exchange, collaboration opportunities, joint activities
MIP	Monthly meetings	Online	Project update, technical exchanges

Table 1. Overview of regular meetings and participation

2.3 Collaboration with Mission components and projects

2.3.1 Joint workshops for monitoring

A key milestone in fostering collaboration and mutual learning and advancing monitoring methodologies within the Mission framework was the 2 in-person workshops held on April 19, 2023, as part of Task 2.3. and on March 3, 2025 as part of European Ocean Week.

These events brought together a diverse array of stakeholders, including representatives from the MIP, other CSAs, and on-the-ground restoration practitioners. The workshops served as a critical platform for exchanging knowledge, aligning perspectives, and co-developing a set of tailored indicators for the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse areas. It significantly enriched the development process by incorporating practical insights into the technical design of the indicators, ensuring their relevance for real-world application.

This collaborative effort not only enhanced the robustness of Deliverable D2.4¹, which outlines a comprehensive and dynamic indicator framework, but also strengthened cross-project integration by anchoring the framework in shared priorities. The dialogue initiated during the first session laid the groundwork for subsequent refinements, with follow-up workshops in 2025, further anchoring these indicators into broader Mission monitoring systems such as WaveLinks and the MIP platform. Ultimately, this workshop exemplified how structured, inclusive exchanges can drive convergence between technical innovation and strategic coordination in support of the Mission's overarching goals.

2.3.2 WaveLinks: A Pivotal Tool for Alignment and Monitoring Collaboration

[WaveLinks.eu](https://www.wavelinks.eu) emerged as a cornerstone of collaboration in the Mission Ocean and Waters ecosystem. Co-developed by BlueMissionAA, PREP4BLUE, and BlueMissionBANOS, WaveLinks has evolved into a multifunctional digital platform designed to support transparency, data sharing, and coordination.

At its core, WaveLinks functions as a shared repository of:

- Monitoring indicators and methods,
- Ongoing restoration projects and their status,
- Stakeholder profiles and networks,
- Citizen science initiatives and engagement practices
- Solutions and services repository.

By early 2025, WaveLinks hosted more than 5,800 restoration-relevant projects, 14,000 institutions, and nearly 1,000 citizen science initiatives, and currently 169 solutions creating an unprecedented dataset for cross-Mission alignment. Within the Atlantic and Arctic basin, it

¹ 2023.BLUEMISSIONAA Report 2023. Development and update of a set of relevant indicators and recommendations for the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse area. 20 pp.

enabled BlueMissionAA to track over 1,500 region-specific projects, with over 100 directly contributing to restoration monitoring.

Figure 2. WaveLinks user interface enables stakeholders to contribute with new project data, enriching the monitoring process and ensuring data quality

The platform's open-access design and contribution-friendly interface ensured that both institutional and grassroots actors could enrich the dataset. Monthly updates and targeted outreach have gradually turned WaveLinks into a "one-stop shop" for identifying who is doing what, where, and how - enabling evidence-based decision-making and reducing duplication across CSAs and RIAs. WaveLinks thus supports a living map of Mission progress, reinforcing both strategic visibility and operational efficiency.

PREP4BLUE D4.6² also provided recommendations to further develop WaveLinks beyond the end of PREP4BLUE and the Missions CSAs, aiming to evolve it into a comprehensive Mission Dashboard that addresses all end-user needs and effectively tracks progress towards the Mission's objectives and targets (see also 5. Recommendations in this report).

² D 4.6 - Report on Mission dashboard concept and findings for tracking of Mission progress

2.3.3 The Mission Implementation Platform (MIP)

The Mission Implementation Platform (MIP) contributed to the monitoring and assessment of the Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters.” It developed a set of 25 input and output indicators at the Mission level and began working in September 2024, in coordination with the European Commission, on defining outcome and impact indicators. To support this process, the MIP prepared a survey addressed to Mission projects and demonstration sites.

The output of this work is the Dashboard which is part of the Mission “Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030” monitoring system. The information displayed shows the progress with Mission implementation to date. In this Monitoring Dashboard, specifically designed indicators are used to track progress towards the Mission Ocean and Waters' objectives and targets. The set of indicators measure the output, outcomes and impacts of all Mission activities.

This dashboard serves as a visual tool for tracking progress toward achieving the Mission's objectives and targets. The tool has the following objectives:

- Provide clear, timely and accurate contextual information on the progress of the Mission
- Provide the ability to produce graphical representations of data
- Provide an interactive interface to enable users to identify relevant actions

BlueMissionAA actively contributed to these efforts by participating in regular exchanges with the MIP and other Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs), ensuring that the specific needs and experiences of the Atlantic-Arctic basin were reflected.

BlueMissionAA also took part in discussions around the creation of a working group on indicators and monitoring and supported the proposal to organise an in-person workshop on these topics during the European Ocean Days 2025 (see 3.1 joint workshops on monitoring). In addition to monitoring, the MIP compiled a catalogue of approximately 160 solutions sourced from the Mission's portfolio, including those identified by BlueMissionAA and its associated implementation actions.

BlueMissionAA shared its solutions via the WaveLinks platform³ and contributed to the joint reflection on their potential for replication and transfer. Moreover, the MIP launched initiatives to promote endorsement of the Mission Charter⁴, aiming to reach 1,000 pledges by the end of 2024; BlueMissionAA supported this effort through exchanges on outreach strategies and communication tools. Throughout these activities, BlueMissionAA maintained close collaboration with the MIP, playing an active role in shaping tools, processes, and shared approaches at Mission level.

³ <https://wavelinks.eu/>

⁴ <https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/restore-our-ocean-and-waters/mission-charter>

3. Mutual learning and best practices Exchange

3.1 Integration of PESTEL-Theory of Change Framework for Mutual Learning

BlueMissionAA played a leading role in advancing mutual learning across Mission Ocean and Waters initiatives by operationalising a combined PESTEL–Theory of Change (ToC) framework, developed under Task 2.4 and led by ICES. This structured methodology enabled a systematic analysis of political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors influencing the entire restoration journey—from planning and implementation to long-term ecological outcomes (task 1.4).

Initially applied within the Atlantic–Arctic basin, the framework served as both a strategic planning tool and a common analytical language. Its adoption by other CSAs demonstrated its value in aligning diverse restoration efforts across basins, enhancing policy coherence, and facilitating knowledge transfer.

Key best practices shared and progressively taken up by other Mission actors included:

- Embedding regulatory foresight—notably references to the EU Nature Restoration Law—into the design of monitoring strategies.
- Adapting stakeholder engagement methodologies tested in various CSAs and shared via platforms like WaveLinks.
- Strengthening governance frameworks by combining top-down institutional mechanisms with bottom-up legitimacy, as illustrated through Mission Arena experiences and regional case studies.

This process of cross-basin exchange, supported through working groups, joint workshops, and knowledge-sharing events, fostered horizontal learning while respecting local context-specific adaptation. By enabling structured planning, investment prioritisation, and ecological monitoring, the PESTEL–ToC approach also positioned BlueMissionAA's work within broader EU policy frameworks and international restoration goals, including those of the UN Decade of Ocean Science.

This methodology and its application were showcased during a dedicated session at the One Ocean Science Congress in Nice on June 5, 2025, aimed at informing marine practitioners, policymakers, and governance experts (see Annex II).

3.2 Mission Monitoring Roundtable

On March 28, 2025, BlueMissionAA participated in the Mission Monitoring Roundtable, a high-level meeting dedicated to advancing the development of a harmonised monitoring framework for the Mission Ocean and Waters.

The discussion brought together key actors from the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP), the European Commission (DG RTD and DG MARE), the European Environment Agency (EEA), and Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs), including BlueMissionAA, BlueMissionBANOS, and BlueMissionMed. The participants collectively recognised the need for a coherent approach to monitoring, with a stronger emphasis on outcomes and impacts aligned with Mission objectives. BlueMissionAA actively contributed to the proposal of a structured framework encompassing inputs, outputs, outcomes, and long-term impacts, and underlined the value of pragmatic, harmonised monitoring guidelines across lighthouses.

The group acknowledged the challenge of capturing long-term impact and proposed the development of pilot projects to test the monitoring framework. Specific metrics - such as the number of innovative actions and the degree of pollution reduction - were suggested. The meeting concluded with a commitment to draft a concept note, extract relevant contributions from ongoing initiatives, and convene a follow-up workshop. The participation of senior policy officers was also identified as essential to ensure policy alignment and effective integration of monitoring efforts.

4. Challenges, Opportunities and Outcomes

4.1 Challenges and opportunities

Despite notable achievements, BlueMissionAA also encountered structural and operational challenges. The asynchronous start of Mission Ocean and Waters projects, coupled with the delay in MIP's activation and the late availability of baseline studies⁵, hindered early alignment. The fragmentation of digital tools and duplication of efforts across CSAs (e.g., multiple helpdesks, databases) created confusion for stakeholders and diluted efficiency.

Further, the diversity of geographical, institutional, and methodological approaches among projects made standardisation of indicators and data flows more complex than anticipated. Efforts to harmonise these practices required extensive negotiation, which slowed the pace of convergence. Additionally, the lack of a common understanding early on regarding the role and impact of Mission components created inconsistencies.

Nonetheless, the project identified significant opportunities to turn these lessons into assets. Shared working groups on indicators are helping to harmonise approaches, and the collaborative dynamic built during the initial phase of Mission implementation has laid a solid foundation for deeper cross-basin integration. The success of platforms like WaveLinks

⁵ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Alao Chanou, Z., McColgan, O., Berbel, J., et al., Baseline study for the implementation of lighthouses of the Mission 'Restore our ocean and waters by 2030': Atlantic, Arctic, Danube and Mediterranean lighthouses, Publications Office of the European Union, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/34856>

in creating a shared data environment, and the growing uptake of mutual learning tools like the PESTEL–ToC framework, demonstrate that ecosystem-wide alignment is possible and underway.

There is also growing momentum to consolidate digital tools and develop clear governance pathways. With the MIP now fully operational and joint events - such as the Mission Monitoring Roundtable -generating political buy-in, BlueMissionAA is well-positioned to influence a more coherent and outcome-driven monitoring framework. The openness of key actors, including the European Commission and other lighthouse CSAs, to collaborative indicator development and workshop-based co-creation signals a wider shift toward transparency, inclusiveness, and pragmatism.

Moving forward, these challenges and opportunities underscore the need for continued investment in strategic coordination, simplification of tools and processes, and sustained mutual learning. By anchoring monitoring in both technical rigour and cross-basin dialogue, BlueMissionAA can continue to contribute to a resilient, adaptive, and mission-aligned monitoring architecture.

4.2 Outcomes and Added Value of Networking & Collaboration

The collaborative framework established under Task 2.4 has yielded tangible benefits that go beyond individual project deliverables, reinforcing both the operational coherence and long-term strategic orientation of the Mission. By fostering synergies across initiatives and actors, the work conducted under this task has:

- **Enabled a more unified monitoring architecture**, built around shared indicators and the integration of interoperable digital tools. This has helped create a common language and approach to track progress, enhance comparability, and support decision-making across diverse contexts.
- **Facilitated the uptake of mutual learning methodologies**, notably the incorporation of the PESTEL-ToC (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, Legal – Theory of Change) framework. This approach has been instrumental in structuring cross-regional reflections, identifying context-specific drivers and barriers, and anchoring strategic foresight into planning processes.
- **Improved alignment and coordination among stakeholders**, spanning local, national, and European levels. This has strengthened multi-level governance, fostered shared priorities, and enhanced the capacity for integrated action across sectors and geographies.
- **Laid the groundwork for evidence-based scaling**, particularly in the Atlantic and Arctic lighthouses, where early alignment on indicators and shared learnings has facilitated the replication and amplification of restoration practices.

Beyond these technical achievements, the networking and collaboration approach promoted by BlueMissionAA has contributed to building a culture of shared ownership, transparent reporting, and dynamic learning. These elements are essential for maintaining

short-term alignment among actors while fostering the adaptive capacity and resilience needed to sustain Mission implementation over time.

5. Recommendations

Building on the progress achieved during the first phase of the Mission, Task 2.4 has identified key strategic and operational levers to enhance coherence, efficiency, and impact as the initiative moves into its next phase. The following recommendations aim to ensure continuity, scalability, and inclusivity across Mission activities:

- **Consider the longer-term use of Wavelinks** as the central integration platform for monitoring data, stakeholder engagement, and solution tracking in the first phase of the Mission. Its role as a digital backbone could be further reinforced to support interoperability across initiatives and streamline reporting.
- **Facilitate ongoing collaboration with Projects (CSAs, RIAs, and IAs)** through dedicated meetings and workshops to jointly develop and refine the Mission Monitoring Framework. Coordination and co-creation of reporting and monitoring frameworks across the Mission Lighthouses, and beyond, is essential to ensure comparability and interoperability. Emphasis should be placed on assessing the collective impact of project portfolios rather than isolated project-level outcomes, enabling a more systemic and mission-oriented evaluation of progress.
- **Streamline digital and governance infrastructures**, reducing fragmentation across Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) and ensuring coherent interfaces with the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP). This will help minimise administrative burdens and improve user experience for stakeholders.
- **Invest in structured capacity-building and cross-basin learning mechanisms**, such as regular Mission forums, inter-basin staff exchanges, and preparatory alignment with emerging frameworks (e.g., the Ocean Pact). These structures are vital for maintaining institutional memory, fostering innovation, and building long-term implementation capabilities.

Taken together, these recommendations support a more integrated, inclusive, and adaptive Mission governance model - essential for sustaining momentum and impact in the next implementation phase.

6. Annexes

- Annex I – List of main joint meetings and workshops
- Annex II – Integrating PESTEL and Theory of Change for scalable Marine Ecosystem Restoration and Governance, abstract One Ocean Science Congress 2025

Annex I – List of main joint meetings and workshops (not an exhaustive list)

Internal Coordination within BlueMissionAA Work Packages:

- Launch of the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse (24th and 25th November 2022, Cork, Ireland): A foundational event that gathered all BlueMissionAA partners and other Mission component representatives to align on the goals and collaborative strategies of the Arctic and Atlantic Lighthouse.
- Monthly and Annual BlueMissionAA Meetings: Regular interactions to discuss project progress, evolve Mission strategies, and maintain alignment with MIP, Secretariat, and the Commission. These included key gatherings in Lisbon (29-30 November 2023) and Brussels (5 March 2024).
- Communication monthly meeting

Coordination with other Mission Ocean and Waters projects:

- CLIMAREST Consortium meeting – 15th-17th April, IFREMER hosted CLIMAREST, a Horizon EU project which sits within the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse. During the Consortium meeting there was a presentation of BlueMissionAA and of PREP4BLUE.
- iMermaid – January 2024 & March 2024 - Exchange between IFREMER representatives and iMermaid.
- Monthly meetings with A-AAGORA and CLIMAREST.

Coordination with other components of the Mission, including other Lighthouses to ensure coherency between EU maritime basins:

- BlueMissionAA's presence at the launch of the Danube & Black Sea Lighthouse – 3rd and 4th of April 2023 (Bucharest, Romania)
- Online participation of BlueMissionAA at the Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse in action – 25th and 26th of April 2023 (Hamburg, Germany); This event was an opportunity to learn about actions implemented by the Baltic and North Sea Lighthouse and exchange best practices. Project: 101093962 — BlueMissionAA — HORIZON-MISS-2021-OCEAN-02 EU Grants: Periodic report/Additional prefinancing report/Beneficiary termination report (HE): V1.1 – 01.05.2023
- Online participation of BlueMissionAA at the Mediterranean Lighthouse in action – 30th and 31th of May 2023 (Palermo, Italy). This event was an opportunity to learn about actions implemented by the Mediterranean Lighthouse and exchange best practices.
- 1st Annual Forum of the Mission Ocean & Waters – 17 February 2023, Brussels: BlueMissionAA WP2 attended the event. During the event BlueMissionAA participants had the chance to interact with the Mission coordination team, including PREP4BLUE, as well as a diverse number of partner institutions.
- Monthly CSA coordinators & MIP meetings
- 2nd Annual Forum of the Mission Ocean & Waters – 5 March 2024, Brussels
- 3rd Annual Forum of the Mission Ocean & Waters – 3 March 2025, Brussels

- BlueMissionAA's Atlantic & Arctic Lighthouse Weekly Hour events: BlueMissionAA organizes weekly webinars that are held on Zoom platform and livestreamed on its YouTube Channel. It aims at promoting Blue Innovation solutions and services using case studies and projects with the public.

Outreach and dissemination activities and events, notably in order to diffuse best practices:

- EuroMarine Open Science Day 2023 – 24 and 25 of May 2023 (Lisbon, Portugal)
- European Maritime Days 2023 – 24th and 25th of May 2023 (Brest, France)
- EU Mission Forum (4-5 March 2024, Brussels): participation to BlueMissionAA side events
- Matchmaking event with other CSAs, (R)IAs and EC, philanthropists, foundations and others (4 March 2024)
- Matchmaking event with BlueInvest (7 March 2024)
- Launch of AAORIA CSA's OKEANO in Brussels – 7 – 8 March 2024
- UN Ocean Decade Conference (10-12 April 2024, Barcelona): participation to BlueMissionAA side events
- "Ocean20" (G20 Event, 8 April 2024)
- "Building a strong scientific community in support of a sustainable Atlantic Ocean" (11 April 2024)
- CLIMAREST Consortium meeting in IFREMER – 15 – 17 April 2024 with BlueMissionAA and A-AAGORA
- 2nd Annual Forum of the Mission Ocean & Waters - 5 March 2024, Brussels
- 3rd Annual Forum of the Mission Ocean & Waters - 3 March 2025, Brussels

Annex II – Integrating PESTEL and Theory of Change for scalable Marine Ecosystem Restoration and Governance, abstract One Ocean Science Congress 2025

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Integrating PESTEL and Theory of Change for scalable Marine Ecosystem Restoration and Governance

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Achieving **sustainable** and **resilient marine ecosystem restoration** requires frameworks that account for both the planned pathway to impact and external influences that shape project success. **PESTEL analysis** (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal) has been piloted in EU projects, such as **FutureMARES** and **ACTNOW**, to assess these factors systematically. Building on these applications, the **BlueMissionAA project** integrates PESTEL with a **Theory of Change (ToC)** framework to align restoration deliverables and inform **governance proposals** in the Atlantic and Arctic Lighthouse areas.

Our approach uses PESTEL to evaluate external factors across each stage of ToC, from **project inputs** to **long-term impacts**, breaking traditional boundaries to provide a holistic pathway for restoration governance. Political and Economic factors shape the feasibility and scalability of restoration activities, while Social engagement and Technological advancements influence local acceptance and monitoring capacity. Environmental conditions, especially **climate impacts**, necessitate adaptive management strategies. Legal frameworks, such as the recent **EU Nature Restoration Law**, exemplify how regulatory shifts can transform barriers into enablers, triggering positive downstream effects across other PESTEL dimensions. By using ToC as a structured pathway, PESTEL insights inform proactive adjustments, ensuring that each deliverable aligns with the project's intended outcomes and is resilient to shifting external conditions.

The integration of **PESTEL** and ToC not only tracks interconnected influences on restoration but also, highlights key opportunities and hindrances, and provides a pathway for translating these insights into **actionable investments** and governance proposals. This approach enhances the monitoring of ecological impacts, strengthens alignment with **EU policy goals**, and fosters adaptive, data-driven decision-making among stakeholders. The combined PESTEL-ToC framework is designed to be adaptable across diverse geographical and political contexts, making it scalable

for applications from local marine protected areas to international ecosystem governance. By being flexible and scalable, the framework aligns with the UN Decade of Ocean Science's goal to **provide adaptable solutions** for diverse marine challenges, ensuring it meets the varied needs of UNOC3 stakeholders.

2025